

ADVANTAGES OF TRAINING HIGHLY MORAL PEDAGOGICAL STAFF IN OUR REPUBLIC

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***Abstract.** This article discusses the reforms aimed at the sphere of education and upbringing without interruptions in our country, currently the state and society are making new requirements for the training of teaching staff for vocational education. These requirements relate primarily to the preparation of mature cadets for the future based on the requirements of modern pedagogical technologies based on the features of vocational education, and information about their particular importance is highlighted.*

***Keywords:** Science-discipline, education-upbringing, reformer, Renaissance foundations, nobility, spirituality, modern teaching staff, modern mass media.*

At present, we all see how fierce the competition is in the world. We can adequately respond to this fierce competition only through the widespread introduction of modern science, high technology and innovation achievements. The developed countries of the world set themselves the task of not only increasing the production of products and bringing them to the market, but also of transitioning to an innovative economy based on deep knowledge and scientific achievements. That is, developing one's economy by creating innovative products, adopting and introducing advanced technologies into production is becoming the main factor of development.

Improving the higher education system, introducing innovative educational technologies into the learning process, educating students with high morale, equipping them with knowledge and practical skills that meet the requirements of world standards largely depends on the personality of the teacher, his level of professional training and skills.

There is a need to strengthen the spiritual and moral content in higher education, to educate young people in the spirit of patriotism based on respect for national values, humanitarianism and high spiritual ideals, and to strengthen their immunity against foreign ideas and ideologies. Psychological knowledge, which is steadily entering most areas of our social life, is gaining importance in increasing the effectiveness of developing a comprehensive professional personality. The use of psychological knowledge in pedagogical activities plays an extremely important role in the purposeful implementation of interpersonal relations, the realization of national identity, and the inculcation of spirituality and values in the minds of young people.

Currently, the issue of professional training, ability, as well as personal qualities of the teacher, his character traits, pedagogical abilities, his professional skills and qualifications, and the formation of educational skills in him, is an urgent issue, and solving this task is the main condition for improving the quality of educational work in the higher education system. As a result of effective research in this field, the features of leading and priority value in the pedagogical activity of a teacher of a higher educational institution have been identified and described. That is, motivation for choosing a teaching profession in psychological studies related to professional

training, formation of pedagogical direction in students; scientific-psychological problems of educational process; psychological sources of teaching skills acquisition, characteristics of development of pedagogical skills, mutual cooperation between student and teacher, psychological foundations of pedagogical communication are revealed.

The teacher is the main organizer of the educational process. It has been determined that the formation of students' general educational preparation and independent, creative thinking, spirituality, education level depends not only on programs and textbooks, but mainly on the teacher, his professional and personal qualities.

The analysis of psychological literature shows that work related to the upbringing of the young generation requires not only special organization and specific qualifications and skills, but also a number of personal psychological characteristics.

A teacher working in higher education institutions should have personal qualities, high spirituality, pedagogical ability, and high level of intellectual potential, which is an important condition for the effectiveness of education. A teacher who educates and educates the young generation must first of all stand out from others with his worldview, ideological-political beliefs, and high spirituality. Pedagogical activity is a complex psychological act that serious students put in front of the teacher.

Pedagogical activity requires the teacher to have a high level of knowledge and culture, the presence of high moral qualities, a high level of emerging activity, a strict and smooth character, pedagogical skills, interaction with students in the educational process, cooperation, and treating them as individuals. A teacher with the above qualities, no matter what subject he teaches, arouses interest and motivation in students in his subject, achieves success in the educational process. A high level of motivation in relation to educational activities activates the student, increases his intellectual potential and, as a result, creates in them independent thinking, self-control, discipline.

Possessing such psychological qualities is the basis of the formation of a mature, qualified specialist.

In short, to adapt the field of science to modern economic requirements, to effectively organize the work of the system that ensures the development of priority directions in our republic in the field of intense competition, and to train highly moral pedagogical personnel is one of the main tasks.

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